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D2.6

3rd Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

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Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D2.6

3rd Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

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Abstract

Deliverable 2.6 provides the third report of the Ethical Advisory Board for GenoMed4All. The 3rd Meeting took place on Monday 20th November 2023 and provided an opportunity for the project to update the EAB external members on the latest developments over 2023.

The key points of development included the completion and signing and execution of three Joint Controller Agreements for each of the Use Cases, further technical developments that place the majority of personal data processing on a Federated Learning infrastructure and finalisation of the approach to develop the Ethical Principles and Quality Assurances for

Deliverable 2.5. There was also reflection on the recently enacted Data Governance Act and the forthcoming AI Act and regulations around the European Health Data Space.

A significant development for the EAB was the appointment of Julie Power from Vasculitis Ireland Awareness to the EAB as an external, independent expert replacing Mahsa Shabani who had to stand down due to other commitments earlier in 2023.

The EAB also welcomed Jorge Alfonso Kurano as Programme Manager for GenoMed4All.

Paul Timmers was unable to join in person and was updated separately. The EAB were satisfied with the developments of the project and supported the proposed approach for handling D2.5. The next meeting will be in twelve months' time.

Keywords

Ethics, data protection, governance, advisory board, risk management.

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Abbreviations

HDs	Haematological diseases
FL	Federated Learning
NN	Neural Network
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
WP	Workpackage
EAB	Ethical Advisory Board
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI

1 Executive summary

Deliverable 2.6 provides the third report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). This report has been compiled after the 3rd EAB meeting held on 20th November 2023.

The EAB members were presented with the updated position with regards the project objectives and progress, the data protection and ethics oversight and assessments for the project. Following the completion of the second meeting and submission of D2.3, GenoMed4All focused its efforts on finalisation of the Joint Controller Agreements (JCA), enhancement of the Federated Learning architecture and development of the recommendations on the ethical principles, quality processes and stakeholder engagements for AI development as will be published in D2.5.

The EAB were informed of the successful completion, signing and execution of three JCAs that each cover one of the use cases for the project. There was also time to reflect on the developments of the Data Governance Act and its recent enactment, the AI Act and the regulations surrounding the European Health Data Space.

Building on the Broad Ethical Principles for GenoMed4All and the Governance Mapping Framework, the EAB were updated on the approach taken for developing the ethical principles for GenoMed4All and similar AI driven projects drawn from the European Commission Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. The Guidelines prescribe seven key requirements to establish trustworthiness for AI and a further Assessment List for Trustworthy AI to measure adherence.

The EAB welcomed a new member of the independent advisors to replace Mahsa Shabani who had stood down last year. Julie Power of Vasculitis Ireland Awareness was formally appointed to the EAB, bringing her experience of working as a patient advocate in rare conditions, specifically vasculitis, and her public and patient engagement and involvement experience, particularly in AI centric projects that access and process patient information.

The EAB also welcomed Jorge Alfonso Kurano as Programme Manager for GenoMed4All.

The EAB were satisfied with the updates and the approach chosen for D2.5. They also agreed to act as reviewers for D2.5, which GenoMed4All is aiming to submit to the European Commission in March 2024. The next EAB meeting will be held in twelve months' time and updates will be provided throughout as and when needed.

2 Introduction

This Deliverable 2.6 provides the third report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). The EAB has been constituted by inviting three independent experts in the area of advanced techniques for using health data to improve outcomes and foster digital innovation.

The EAB goal is to provide an independent view on the ethical robustness of the project and its activities across the consortium partners with specific focus on its protection of data and ethical AI development.

For the third report, the EAB has considered updates and developments relating to ethical and regulatory requirements for GenoMed4All in line with their role as defined in Deliverable 2.2, the first report of the EAB.

2.1 Development of GenoMed4All and Updates

After the series of meetings with the EAB members throughout November 2022, GenoMed4All finalised three Joint Controller Agreements (JCA) to cover each of the Use Cases within the Project. The finalised JCAs were agreed and signed by all partners and executed in the first quarter of 2023 after a series of final reviews.

Further details are available in D2.3, which includes the data sharing agreements and description of the approach taken to develop them. The development and history of EAB involvement is also described in D2.4 in detail.

Following the host of Member State regulatory changes as described in D2.4, GenoMed4All has also kept a close watch on the enactment of the Data Governance Act as well as the evolution of the AI Act and regulations surrounding the European Health Data Space.

Further to the work on developing core ethical principles for GenoMed4All, the preparations for developing Deliverable 2.5 for establishing the recommendations on the ethical principles, quality processes and stakeholder engagements for AI development have advanced. The EAB was updated with the specifics surrounding the approach and development of these materials and their involvement in its review was sought.

Additionally developments with the Data Governance and Artificial Intelligence Acts and the European Health Data Space, has compelled GenoMed4All to consider its approaches in line with these developments.

2.2 Structure of this report

This report describes in Section 3 the developments in the Project since the last series of EAB meetings and publication of D2.4. Section 4 updates on the action items from the last EAB and next steps.

The report concludes with proposed next steps and the next meeting of the EAB.

3 Developments Since the November 2022 EAB Meetings and Activities for 2024

There have been several project related and wider regulatory and pan European developments that are described in this section.

3.1 EAB Constitution

As described in D2.4, a series of personnel changes meant that the EAB constitution changed. Mahsa Shabani stood down as an independent expert and has been replaced by Julie Power of Vasculitis Ireland Awareness. Additionally Jorge Alfonso Kurano joined GenoMed4All as its Programme Manager.

The members of the EAB are therefore now as follows (in alphabetical order):

- ❑ **Federico Álvarez (UPM, WP1 Lead and Project Co-ordinator, Internal)**
- ❑ **Tommaso Foglia (DataWizard, WP2 Member, Internal)**
- ❑ **Nikolaus Forgó (Independent Expert EAB Member, Professor of IT and IP Law, University of Vienna, External)**
- ❑ **Dipak Kalra (i~HD, WP2 Lead, Internal)**
- ❑ **Jorge Alfonso Kurano (UPM, WP1 Member, Programme Manager, Internal)**
- ❑ **Nathan Lea (i~HD, WP2 Lead, Internal)**
- ❑ **Julie Power (Independent Expert EAB Member Vasculitis Ireland Awareness, External)**
- ❑ **Anna Rizzo (Data Wizard, WP2 Member, Internal)**
- ❑ **Paul Timmers (Independent Expert EAB Member, Research Associate University of Oxford, Former EU Director European Commission, External)**

The third EAB Meeting was held on Monday 20th November 2023 where the updates were provided to the EAB and approved.

3.2 Finalisation, Signing and Execution of the Joint Controller Agreements.

Further to the updates provided in D2.4, the JCAs were finalised and described, signed by all partners and executed in the first quarter of 2023. Three JCAs were prepared to cover each use case for Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), Multiple Myeloma (MM) and Myelodysplastic Syndrome (MDS). In each case, all parties were identified as Joint Controllers except for DEDALUS, which holds a Processor role, and CINECA, which holds a sub-processor role. These roles are all clearly established in the JCAs and all parties are operating within their contractual obligations.

Along with the Data Protection Impact Assessments the JCAs will continue to be monitored throughout 2024. Should there be any major compliance challenges, issues or breaches, the

DPIA will be reviewed along with the impact on the execution of the JCAs. The oversight and update of these materials is now entering a “business as usual” phase where routine review every six months is prescribed best practice in the absence of any other critical issues arising in the meantime.

3.3 Ethical Principles, Quality Processes and Stakeholder Engagements for AI Development

After the publication of D2.4, the key areas of focus for the Project in terms of ethics and wider governance were to ensure that the JCAs were well established in their execution for the Project and helped to guide the implementation and data handling. The operation of the project has continued in line with these agreements and the wider Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) expectations which means that the Project can focus on the D2.5 provision for ethical principles, quality processes and stakeholder engagements.

After the EAB meetings in November 2022, the following set of broad principles were agreed after the stakeholder engagement that had been performed throughout 2021 and 2022:

- ❑ Where possible, ensure that data transfers are minimised to protect the rights and interests of participants. This shall not introduce risk of bias, error or quality degradation in the algorithm development, where sharing of training data must occur if there could be a significant risk.
- ❑ Make use of synthetic data where possible, mindful that algorithms must be validated on real data to be better assured as to accuracy and value.
- ❑ The use of identifiable, anonymous or pseudonymised data (either for training or in cases where sharing is required) must occur within the bounds of existing consent and Independent Review Board Opinions. Where consent is not possible¹, an IRB view must be sought for a view on whether this is appropriate.

These elements need to form the basis of the ethical principles and quality processes development and these are enhanced by the experience of implementing and executing the JCAs. In terms of framing the particulars of GenoMed4All, the Governance Compliance Mapping diagram agreed by the EAB back in 2022 will be a primary basis to drive this forward.

¹ Consent is impossible in the case of deceased individuals, and may be impossible in cases where individuals are lost to follow up or otherwise uncontactable. They may also have expressed a wish to be contacted again but their wishes about data access are not clear.

The EAB were notified that further to their advisory in 2022 the approach taken for developing the ethical principles for GenoMed4All and similar AI driven projects are drawn from the European Commission Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence². The Guidelines prescribe seven key requirements to establish trustworthiness for AI as follows:

1. human agency and oversight
2. technical robustness and safety
3. privacy and data governance
4. transparency
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. environmental and societal well-being and
7. accountability

In order to assess against these, an Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)³ to measure adherence has been proposed. This introduces a list of questions under each requirement heading that need to be answered to assure some degree of compliance with the requirements specifications, but it also serves as a basis for the development of ethical and operational principles.

The recommendations from the EAB were to use the ALTAI and the toolkits for their assessment. Unfortunately the assessment toolkits implementing the assessment of the list items in the list has been delayed and is still under development.

The list itself is comprehensive, and GenoMed4All proposed to the EAB meeting that WP2 use the existing high level principles to establish the detailed ethical principles based on the experiences and stakeholder engagement that the Project have had. This can help derive more

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

detailed ethical principles. WP2 can then take the ALTAI items and attempt to answer each one of the assessment questions in order to verify to a degree the robustness of the quality processes and stakeholder engagements that form the basis of the ethical principles development.

The EAB were satisfied with this approach and WP2 will work to have a draft ready for review by mid February 2024 for the EAB to consider.

3.4 Regulatory and European Developments

Further to the points raised in the November 2022 EAB meetings, the EU has now enacted the Data Governance Act and has revised the draft of the AI Act. The regulations surrounding the EHDS also continue to be developed. The AI Act and EHDS are due to be enacted in late 2024 and early 2025 respectively.

The primary implications of the AI Act and EHDS for GenoMed4All relate to the need for certifications for High Risk AI Interventions from competent and notifiable authorities, adherence in line with the ALTAI and Ethical AI requirements, and the ability to operate with full cataloguing and data integrity as per the EHDS.

From these perspectives the shifting regulatory landscape seems to emphasise the need for assurance around data management and handling. The approach that GenoMed4All has taken to establish the ethical principles via the ALTAI is also a potential test run for the forthcoming assessment frameworks that will likely be in place to assure compliance with the AI Act.

4 Conclusions

The progress of GenoMed4All throughout 2023 has occurred during a background of increasing regulatory changes and wider societal expectation shifts around the use of AI and reuse of health and other personal data. The shift towards a federated learning model combined with the completion of the JCAs has helped to put the Project on a more justifiable and robust footing as the architecture is finalised and data starts to be processed.

This report to the EAB has highlighted the current progress of the Project and has established the basis upon which the articulation of the ethical principles, quality processes and how the stakeholder engagements have occurred. The report also describes the approach for addressing those regulatory changes and how GenoMed4All can remain not only compliant, but also trustworthy to the wider citizenry.

The EAB will review the draft of D2.5 around mid February 2024 and will meet again in the fourth quarter of 2024.

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